

Experimental Setup for the CEC 2026 Competition on Multimodal Multiobjective Optimization

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Abstract

This report describes the benchmark problems, performance measures, and experimental setup used for participation in the CEC 2026 competition on multimodal multi-objective optimization. The MATLAB implementations of the benchmark problems and the performance indicators are also provided.

1 Introduction

Multimodal multiobjective optimization (MMO) [1] can be perceived as the integration of multimodal optimization [2] into multiobjective optimization [3]. The goal of MMO is to detect the entire Pareto set (PS), even though a fraction of it can represent the entire Pareto front (PF). A promising method for MMO should be able to balance conflicting goals of convergence, diversity in the decision and objective spaces properly.

The CEC 2026 competition on multimodal multiobjective optimization¹ aims to offer a fair and comprehensive platform for benchmarking MMO methods. It employs a recent scalable test suite for MMO and a recent overall performance indicator proposed in [4].

2 Theoretical Background

The primary advantage of MMO over more traditional multi-objective optimization methodologies is its ability to provide the decision-maker with a diverse set of solutions once the desired trade-off among problem objectives has been identified. These alternative solutions can account for aspects of the actual problem that may have been overlooked when formulating the mathematical model, as well as those aspects that are inherently difficult to formalize [5].

A standard box-constrained MMO problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize } \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_M(\mathbf{x})]^T, \\ & \text{subject to } \mathbf{L} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{U}, \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

in which $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ is the fitness vector of the solution \mathbf{x} , M is the number of objectives, also referred to as the problem dimensionality in the objective space, and \mathbf{L} and \mathbf{U} are the lower and upper bounds of the search space.

Figure 1 illustrates a typical outcome of MMO for a problem with two identifiable Pareto set regions (PSRs), where the first region maps to the entire Pareto front (PF), while the second maps only to a portion of it. From a traditional multi-objective optimization perspective, an ideal outcome may place all reported solutions on \mathbf{PSR}_1 , since this region corresponds to the full PF. In contrast, an MMO method should be capable of approximating \mathbf{PSR}_2

¹<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmmoocec2026>

Figure 1: A typical outcome of MMO for a problem with two identifiable Pareto set regions (PSRs), in which the first one maps to the entire PF, whereas the second one maps to a fraction of it.

at the same time, thereby providing alternative solutions once the desired trade-off among objectives has been determined by the decision-maker.

3 Test Problems

The test suite consists of eight problem families with 2 to 5 objectives, and each is tested with 4 or 5 values for D , resulting in 37 problems, which are denoted by $PID = 1, 2, \dots, 37$ (see Table 1). These problems present diverse challenges, including the presence of PSRs with different shapes, sizes, orientations, and attraction regions. More importantly, each PSR may map to only a fraction of the Pareto front (PF), and besides, it is likely that a smaller PSR maps to a larger part of the PF. For each representative point on the PF, there are 1 to 5 points on the PS. More detailed information on these test problems can be found in [4].

For each problem, 10 instances were defined ($PIN = 1, 2, \dots, 10$) to compensate for the randomness in the generation process. All problem instances are deterministic as the random numbers are read from predefined sets.

Table 1: Employed composite MMO problems and their dimensionalities in the objective space (M) and the decision space (D).

PID	Problem Family	Base MOP	M	D
1	CMMOP1	ZDT 1	2	3
2	CMMOP2	ZDT 3	2	3
3	CMMOP3	DTLZ 2	3	3
4	CMMOP4	DTLZ 4	3	3
5	CMMOP5	DTLZ 7	3	3
6	CMMOP1	ZDT 1	2	5
7	CMMOP2	ZDT 3	2	5
8	CMMOP3	DTLZ 2	3	5
9	CMMOP4	DTLZ 4	3	5
10	CMMOP5	DTLZ 7	3	5
11	CMMOP6	DTLZ 2	5	5
12	CMMOP7	DTLZ 4	5	5
13	CMMOP8	DTLZ 7	5	5
14	CMMOP1	ZDT 1	2	10
15	CMMOP2	ZDT 3	2	10
16	CMMOP3	DTLZ 2	3	10
17	CMMOP4	DTLZ 4	3	10
18	CMMOP5	DTLZ 7	3	10
19	CMMOP6	DTLZ 2	5	10
20	CMMOP7	DTLZ 4	5	10
21	CMMOP8	DTLZ 7	5	10
22	CMMOP1	ZDT 1	2	20
23	CMMOP2	ZDT 3	2	20
24	CMMOP3	DTLZ 2	3	20
25	CMMOP4	DTLZ 4	3	20
26	CMMOP5	DTLZ 7	3	20
27	CMMOP6	DTLZ 2	5	20
28	CMMOP7	DTLZ 4	5	20
29	CMMOP8	DTLZ 7	5	20
30	CMMOP1	ZDT 1	2	30
31	CMMOP2	ZDT 3	2	30
32	CMMOP3	DTLZ 2	3	30
33	CMMOP4	DTLZ 4	3	30
34	CMMOP5	DTLZ 7	3	30
35	CMMOP6	DTLZ 2	5	30
36	CMMOP7	DTLZ 4	5	30
37	CMMOP8	DTLZ 7	5	30

4 Experimental Setup

Each problem instance should be optimized four times with different random seed numbers. Given 37 problems (see Table 1) and 10 instances for each problem, a total of $37 \times 10 \times 4 = 1480$ optimization runs should be performed.

For all problems, the evaluation budget is $2500 \times D \times M$. The size of the final (reported) population—not necessarily the population size used during the optimization process—should be $\lfloor 50 \times \sqrt{D \times M} \rfloor$. If the reported population has more members, only the first $\lfloor 50 \times \sqrt{D \times M} \rfloor$ solutions will be considered for performance assessment. Notably, the population size during optimization may be larger or smaller than this number.

4.1 Performance Indicator

We employ $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$ —an overall parametric performance indicator proposed in [4] for MMO—to measure the quality of the reported population. For a smaller $\alpha > 0$, this indicator emphasizes detection of diverse solutions (success from the multimodal optimization perspective), whereas for a greater $\alpha > 0$, it emphasizes accuracy of approximation of the PF. $\alpha = 1$ can be interpreted as equal importance of each perspective [4]. While the performance of participating methods will be analyzed for different values of α , ultimately $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$ with $\alpha = 0.7$ will be used to rank the methods. The code of this indicator, as well as a simple example to calculate performance using this indicator, are provided on the competition website². More detailed information on $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$ can be found in [4].

Given $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$ as the performance indicator, the final ranking of methods will be determined using the Friedman test with a significance level of 0.05, calculated over 370 problem instances with $n_{\text{rep}} = 4$.

4.2 Parameter Setting

No ad-hoc tuning is allowed, and the participants should present the tuning process of their method. The following features of problems are assumed to be known a priori and can be used for parameter setting:

- Problem dimensionality in the decision space (D) and objective space (M)

²<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmmoocec2026>

- Search space bounds
- Evaluation budget and the size of the reported final population
- The use $\alpha = 0.7$ for the performance indicator.
- Iteration/Evaluation count during the optimization process

5 Using the Code

The standalone code of the performance indicator and test problems in MATLAB has been provided on the competition website³. See the file 'example_problem_generation.m') for a simple example explaining how to use the benchmark problems. In particular the user can create the problem object as follows:

```
problem=ProblemComposite(prbNo,instanceID)
problem.set_problem_data()
```

Once the object `problem` was created and formed:

- `problem.func_eval(x)` calculates the fitness vectors of solution(s) x , which can be a matrix in which each row is a solution.
- `problem.maxEval` and `problem.numCallF` return the evaluation budget and the number of calls to the function evaluations so far, respectively. Make sure the number of used evaluations is less than or equal to the evaluation budget at the end of the optimization run.
- `problem.lowBound` and `problem.upBound` return the lower and upper bounds of the search space.
- `problem.dim` returns the search space dimensionality.

More detailed data on the problem, including the PS and PF are also accessible from the object `problem`, although they must not be used for optimization.

The file `example_calc_IGED.m` shows how $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$ is calculated given the reported solutions for a typical problem and defined values of α . Notably, the

³<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmmoocec2026>

fitness vectors of both population members and PF representative solutions should be normalized for the calculation of $IGED_{\alpha}^{+}$.

6 Submission Instructions

The participants are encouraged to provide a PDF file describing their method. The PDF file will be uploaded to the competition website after the announcement of the results. If the method is already published, they may simply provide the reference.

A zipped folder of $37 \times 10 \times 4 = 1480$ CSV files should be provided, one CSV file for each optimization run. The name of each file should be “pid**_pin**_run**.csv”. For example, for the third run of $PID=5$ with $PIN=2$, the name of the file should be “pid05_pin02_run03.csv”.

Each file should contain the solutions reported by the method (columns 1 to D) and their fitness values (columns $D+1$ to $D+M$). The fitness vectors of these solutions will be recalculated during performance assessment; therefore, solutions should be submitted with sufficiently high precision. A sample of the result files is available on the competition website⁴.

References

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